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Intelligent security system for access doors based on the implementation of CNN on FPGA board

Bouchra KOUACH¹, Mohcin Mekhfioui², Rachid El gour³

¹Laboratory of Advanced Systems Engineering, ENSA, Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra, Morocco, bouchra.kouach@uit.ac.ma

²Faculty of Science, University Ibn Tofail, Kenitra, Morocco, mohcin.mekhfioui@uit.ac.ma

³Laboratory of Advanced Systems Engineering, ENSA, Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra, Morocco, elgourirachid@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, there's a great deal of interest in the security of digital data, but it's crucial to recognize that the physical protection of equipment containing sensitive information is essential. Indeed, the loss of a server is the same as the loss of data. With this in mind, this article proposes an intelligent security system for datacenter room access doors, to guarantee optimum protection. To this end, this work seeks to implement a door security system based on image classification by the CNN convolutional neural network applied to the FPGA board. Our approach is to use deep learning frameworks such as TensorFlow and Keras for model development and training. In terms of FPGA type, we're using the ZYNQ board. To deploy this accelerated CNN model, we use PetaLinux. The results of this work demonstrate that there is an energy saving over the traditional CPU or GPU implementation of CNN. In addition, FPGAs are well adapted to the parallel nature of CNN computations in real-time applications.

Key words : CNN, FPGA, Zynq, PNQY, PetaLinux, Tensorflow, Keras, Image classification, Python.

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